

English Language as an Employment Skill in Diploma Engineering Course serves for Socio Economic Empowerment

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Abstract

Employment opportunity to the youth brings economic prosperity to a country. And diploma engineering education aims at empowerment of the youth with employability skills. The present study aims to develop LSRW skills with technical skills of the technocrats in their respective core engineering along with computer skills and the basic areas of software skills in the age of computer technology. This combination is an effective powerpack employability skill to enable the present generation students undergoing diploma engineering education. The 21st century technical age is an e-world and e-education is economical being easily available but dependent on English language. Also, the language dominating the software and digital world is the English Language. The research highlights on the different areas which provides a concrete and an earnest scope for employment to the undergraduate engineers. The youth population in India being the highest in the world, an empowerment to this population with the relevant employability skills will undoubtedly bring a significant economic development with sustainable livelihood to the economical weaker section. This research dictates inadequate research materials on the objectives of diploma education for employment opportunities to bring a rise in the standards of living of the people. The English language skills, digital literacy skills and digital technology skills will definitely empower the technocrats to reach the altitude of their career. In addition to these, implementation of the teaching methodology in English by both English faculties and technical faculties will enable the engineering students to meet the demands of Global job markets. The study urges further research while emphasizing on the combination of the dynamic skills which acts as a siren announcing an emergency call for efficient technocrats to make the slogan of “Made in India” and “Made in Odisha” successful.

Keywords: *Communication, Employment, Engineering, Empowerment, Digital Technology, Technocrats, Economically Weak.*

1. INTRODUCTION

English as a Corporate language has become a life-line of professional courses in today's cut-throat competitions. The undergraduate engineering institutes need to revise the curriculum of the three years of course to enable the students improve in their skills and efficiency to satisfy the expectations of industry/ MNCs. The English language as “a language of opportunities” should be integrated throughout the curriculum to create links between technical efficiency and Communication skills. A good competency in the language inspires the students to learn the fundamental concepts in both theory and analytical papers. Also, they feel -at-ease to go beyond syllabus to gain a good depth in their technical papers. Diploma engineering course is a low investment course and mostly preferred by the weaker economic section to provide their child a better social status.

Also, the basic objective of Diploma Engineering Course is to provide employment and thus empower the youth. Therefore, inclusion of LSRW skills of English in the curriculum is crucial. The research paper aims to highlight the various survival skills of a diploma engineering student which can be well-groomed with a competent communicative skill in English. This study delves into the various ways in which educators can train students to be successful in the modern workplace.

Communicative English and Diploma Engineering Education:

No doubt an explanation of the technical papers in regional language gives a clear idea of the technical papers to the undergraduate engineers in the beginning of the course during 1st and 2nd semester but along with this enough focus need to be built within the teenagers to be friendly with the corporate language.

The confidence to speak and write good English is to be built within students as semester exam is appeared with English writing in the answer sheets. Regular adequate training classes on spoken English will enable them to perform better in all 6 no. of semesters. With proficiency in English, students can understand technical papers, improve in soft skills, life skills, computer skills, requisite software skills and all these multiple skills will equip them to be competent skilled technocrats to meet the demands of the ever-changing corporate world.

As youth % in India is the highest, employment to the teenagers will result in socio-economic empowerment which in the long run will help in nation-building. Engineers work in team in diverse culture, this international language can create cultural awareness within the teenagers. An acceptance to the global language builds a sound personality to overcome intercultural barriers.

The present research invites rigorous works to make the objective of diploma engineering education a success with low financial investment and to enable the undergraduates to get an entry to the numerous job opportunities and bring an upliftment of the weaker section of society and thus contribute for a self-sufficient society.

A Bridge to Higher Academic Performance:

More than 80% students in Diploma Engineering Institutions in Bhubaneswar come from regional medium schools of various districts of Odisha. The technical papers with its technical jargons become a burden for them.

Only after a session of Spoken English classes in the Induction Programme in 1st semester, students are able to create a good vision of the courses/engineering programmes in which they have been admitted. The institutions providing quality education undertake this responsibility of developing the LSRW skills of students which is drastically missing.

The study finds there is a huge gap in the teaching pedagogy of the undergraduate institutions. Lack of encouragement and motivation of both English and technical faculties leads to either discontinuation of studies by students or lack of interest on the part of students which gradually results in piling up of back papers.

The result analysis of the three years course is far away from satisfactory level as only countable undergraduate engineering students either go for placements or higher studies after completion of the course, and many just do nothing. This results in a rise in educated unemployment. The only reason behind this is their nightmare for this international language which rules the corporate world market of technology.

The Global Language plays a Vital role in Social Upliftment:

We are in the era of third revolution of communication which has paved its way towards an e-world where e-communication has become the life line. The study highlights on different facts with which technocrats can gain the best of the technical knowledge by surfing the internet in an effective way. The present study emphasizes on the streamlining of English Language Teaching in high schools which has been severely overlooked and uncared-for. Therefore, faculties in engineering institutes must act as facilitators to improve LSRW skills, provide students new learning experiences and training on Presentation skills. An engineering student though an average in academic performance but a good flare in the international language and verbal ability matches very much to the competitive exams of engineering and also other fields of public and private sector jobs. Being employed and financially sound from a tender age brings social upliftment in society.

The Vehicle of Expression for Creative Thinking:

The Global job market undergoes significant transformation due to shifts in employment patterns, technological advancement, economic globalization etc. The study finds in students lack of soft skills and challenges to apply theoretical knowledge to different practical contexts. An interactive skill in English helps technocrats to acquire competent and effective marketing skills as per their professional demands. The most essential survival skills of 21st century are decision-making skills, marketing skills, negotiation skills and conflict management skills. Interpersonal tactful communications help the technocrats to meet the demands of the clients and customers satisfactorily; both within India and abroad. Training in Language skills during student life can work miraculously to achieve professional success.

A bridge to Software Skills and jobs in Tech Industries:

Keywords play an important role in Self-learning software Skills or that of Courses through Online mode. Reading skills in English enriches students with strong vocabulary with which students can easily access the online courses on software from YouTube and also courses provided by numerous organisations of both government and private sectors. Software jobs demand proficiency in English. In the tech-industry, companies select candidates who can engage with diverse teams and understand global market needs (**What-is-the-importance-of-English-to-a-software-engineer**).

Self-Motivation for Project Works:

The present technical age is an e-world. The online courses / studies have served the current generation with numerous career opportunities. The Youtube, Reels, innovative technical idea sites etc. are flooded with wonderful project ideas. Latest knowledge on the advancement in technology creates an inspiring zeal and passion within the technocrats to develop innovative ideas for project works and to invent something new.

Any student with a good spark of English skills will be inspired and passionate to search and watch the videos of amazing project ideas related to his syllabus and be an expert influencer in his peer group by trying his hand in completing good no. of project models in each semester. This practice can ignite the young technocrats and illuminate their technical concepts and ideas.

So, it is very essential to make the students friendly with the language with which they can have wings of imagination to their technical ideas. This kind of activity-oriented learning in technical education of the geographical area of this research study is unfortunately not entertained.

Seminar Presentations:

The 21st century Technical Age is a world of preparation, projection and presentation. Being friendly with the international language, students actively participate in preparing seminar reports and anxiously present their reports in a confident manner. Unfortunately, the no. of participants is only 5 % in each undergraduate diploma engineering institute in Bhubaneswar. The research covers 4 of the institutes in its geographical area of Bhubaneswar and finds this shocking result. The race to complete the syllabus is the only priority of faculties in technical institutes. This horrible practice in the duration of 3 years of course ends in facilitating a Diploma Engineering Certificate to students with absolutely no skill to be employed. This way students lack the confidence to represent their technical ideas in English, also avoid appearing the off-campus placement drives as they fail to compete with students of other institutes.

Internship Training and Presentation:

Internship training programmes equip the diploma students with best technical skills and also bridge the gap between the theoretical knowledge and its application in professional scenario. Engineering Students during the training can get a first-hand-knowledge of the workplace culture and also corporate mannerism and behaviorism. Aspiring students develop a rich insight with these training programmes. But still there are students who show no zeal in these trainings. Mentors need to take responsibility to encourage students in a better way to make the training fruitful with students taking interest in gaining technical knowledge. A one month of this technical training only motivates countable no. of students, still these students hardly are able to make a good presentation of the training they have undergone in a month time. Being in a tech savvy age, students display no craziness in technical knowledge. Good students only need a good percentage in diploma engineering education. Until and unless they develop an insight to make a good presentation of the acquired training, it's difficult on their part to meet the industry expectations. The technical institutes need to realise that engineers with communication skills in English can only be a participant of the community of engineers and in the large scale play a vital role in nation-building.

A rigorous practice of presentation skills has to be undertaken by the technical institutions so that student in a natural manner be passionate to undertake e-internship training to equip themselves with latest and innovative technical trainings; and ignite ideas beyond syllabus. Numerous organisations are providing e-internship training to empower technocrats with employability skills of job market. In an urgent level, Language faculties in co-ordination with technical faculties need to shoulder this responsibility for their students.

Digital transformation in Education and Workplace:

During the pandemic period of 2020, the nook and corner of the world experienced a wave of digital transformation. But to what extent it has a positive impact on the education in India? Rather a detail study has shown that it was a great failure in the field of education in India. Teenagers in the age group of 15-20 years of age have deteriorated in their studies with misuse of the digital classroom teaching. The main reason being their inability and unfriendliness with the foreign language. Thus, their access to the gadget remained restricted to entertainment in a false world. The technical students have no vision of using the internet to collect engineering study materials or undertake mini-project works being comfortable at home. Proficiency in the language motivates students to think out of the box and learn innovative things related to science and technology. E-education is economical and accurately

beneficial to all. Students with economically weak backgrounds can take help of engineering learning online sites to read, learn and practice on the competitive areas for better job options with minimum of investments in hardcopies of textbooks. Lack of knowledge on keywords of window language to surf the internet makes them feel sluggish, helpless and frustrated.

Language and Digital Literacy:

In the Age of Digital world, it is essential for the technocrats to be digitally literate with the requisite computer skills. The rapid advancement in Computer Technology is spreading its root deep into all fields. Now this makes them depended on the window language. A friendly approach to the international language will create a comfort zone to explore various computer skills. All electronics windows operate with the use of English Language and surfing is done with the correct keywords. Likewise with a focused brainstorming, technocrats can invest time to learn through online mode from Youtube the necessary computer skills and practice accordingly. Efficient skills in MS word, MS Excel and also LinkedIn, Youtube, Blogger accounts guide in an intellectual manner to explore their technical ideas and develop an insight for technical writings. In the age of ChatGPT and AI, it's very essential for technocrats of the 21st century to go beyond the state boundaries and be updated with the latest technical innovations to equip themselves with industry-readiness tools during their studentship. The study finds all the above-mentioned areas highly neglected in the engineering institutions which is really unacceptable and aghast in this global world of cut-throat competition.

Digital Language Laboratories:

Here the question arises – Do undergraduate engineering students have access to the Digital language laboratories of their institutions? The right answer being – NO. The laboratories are used only as a model digital classroom. Hardly digital lab classes are allotted in regular class routines in the diploma engineering institutions. This study will pave further research works to highlight on the benefits of digital language laboratories so that students are provided an access to the Course Modules and Career Modules of the said laboratory to learn the language in a better manner. These lab classes develop their speaking ability in English with correct pronunciation; also improves their verbal ability skills. Also, the videos on mock-interviews prepare them in an excellent way to be a good participant in all soft skill areas, improves their GD presentations and enables them to crack in personal interviews of Campus Drives. There are a lot of lacunae in this area which need to be improved to make the students employable with diploma engineering education.

English Language Acts as a Window to the World:

Advancement in Technology cannot be restricted within boundaries. Its impact is a global revolution. In a similar way, a student of engineering needs to expand his vision globally. It is the duty of both language and technical faculties to broaden the technical outlook of their students by encouraging them to explore on the technical papers taught in the different semesters within the duration period of 3 years. Numerous sites are available which students can easily explore only with appropriate jargons as keywords to access the sites and gain innovative ideas on scientific and technical fields. Thus, this language provides technocrat a window to the world of technical revolution which in the long run help students to choose their career goal on specific engineering. This development has been marked especially in the students coming from economically weaker sections with a hungry for job at any cost with completion of their 3 years of diploma engineering course. Emphasis on productive trainings is the best solution to settle the youths with a job. Adequate research work on this criterion can

bring productive results: LSRW Skills + Survival Skills + Technical Knowledge = Good Job. Youths with job results in financial prosperity and better standard of living in a society and further prosperous society builds a developed nation.

Access to Online Courses on Digital Technology:

Effective use of digital lab classes would ignite a craziness within them to easily access the available Online Software Courses. There is high demand of software skills in all branches of engineering fields to manage the day-to-day activities in the workplace. In addition to branch papers, students of all branches of diploma engineering should undergo the courses like Coding, Python, Word Processing, Operating Systems, Artificial Intelligence, Database management, etc. Free online classes are provided by different organisations. Therefore, an easy understanding of the window language can create a comfort zone within students and be motivated to undertake the online software courses. All these skills help them to build a strong resume document in their final years to perform well in campus drives. Honing the software skills, they widen the horizon of job opportunities. Thus, a good proficiency in English is highly required. **Mr. B. Sanyasi Rao (RJOE, Vol.-5, Issue-2, 2020, Page-304)** has rightly mentioned that - "Mere knowledge over core skills in the respective field does not guarantee them to secure a good job or to excel at the workplace arena."

The software skills play a vital role in the age of third revolution of communication in getting a job. But unfortunately, along with the increase in the number of diploma engineering institutions there is an equivalent increase of unemployment since a decade. There is no motivation to students by faculties for these software skills. Out of the 4 no. of institutions of the research study, only a single institute has made mandatory to undergo a minimum of 2 to 3 online software courses to be eligible to seat in campus placement. Mostly, the focus being only on completion of the syllabus within deadline. As such the learning ability of students and training area is greatly avoided in the undergraduate engineering education. Only the students from economically weak background; in need of job on urgent basis, competently equip themselves with software skills from Youtube videos.

Student-Centric activities:

Student -centric activities are in syllabus with weekly one period. But no such class is taken in actual practice in the undergraduate engineering institutes. In professional course, these classes connect students to professional life and creates an urge to build the survival skills with a futuristic vision of career to be achieved. Actually, the main defect lies in the lack of life skills and innovative ideas in technical faculties.

The practice of student centric activities like quiz competitions on technical papers and general knowledge, technical writings of seminar papers and project works and then presentations on it, word games with technical jargons, also games on team work and leadership activities can create a passion to work hard in developing a radiant and sound personality with soft skills to achieve a career. Unfortunately, none of these activities is undertaken and allotted.

Engineering and English are complimentary to each other:

Engineering and technology are a global perspective. Innovative ideas of engineers encourage them to look beyond national boundaries for inspiration and solutions, fostering innovation and driving technological progress. Aspiration, inspiration in addition to motivation leads to new advancement in technology. Technocrats on a continuous basis need to keep

adding to academic landscapes to learn and grow professionally (**why-pursuing-a-diploma-in-engineering**). English communication skills enable an engineer to reflect the technical knowledge confidently in global platform. **Mohamed Rabie highlights (Language and Life, 2023, Page- 1)** that- “However, if one knows an international language his world will become borderless and his access to knowledge limitless.” Thus, a rigorous learning and practice of the LSRW skills while learning the syllabus papers can also be helpful to students to develop an accurate fluency in the language. The technical jargons will enable students make good presentations on their technical papers. This would further enhance their performance in both written exams and interviews of campus drives. In this regard, faculties teaching technical papers also need to work to guide students to develop rich technical jargons in course of their theory and practical classes.

Competency Skills:

Engineering students aspiring for placement in both in-campus and off-campus should work persistently on their technical FAQs, reasoning and aptitude skills, verbal ability skills, soft skills and above all the survival skills to meet the challenges in workplace. Developing on all these areas is a gradual process which requires a systematic approach. Only a few days of training classes on all the mentioned areas has not been proved successful for campus placement. It is because their fluency on the language has remained the same as it was since their admission to the course in 1st year. No work has been undertaken to develop the speaking and writing skills of the majority of students. Communicative skill in English will provide them a blooming path to – surf the different sites in internet to explore new ideas/ new inventions, understand the lessons of aptitude and reasoning, learn the verbal ability skills, improve on soft skills and encourage students to read on the achievements of great personalities. Case studies of successful persons and the vigour of epic heroes can guide their conscience and provide the right direction in life to achieve a goal. Self-discovery, self-awareness, self-understanding, self-analysis is urgently required in the personality of students to recognize their own strength. All these will help them in conflict management and in emotional intelligence areas. Also, career in sales and marketing is slowly deepening its grip in production and manufacturing sectors where engineers need to possess good communicative skills along with marketing and negotiation skills.

Those students going through the hardships of pursuing the course with student educational loans or their own economic condition develop the iron-willed confidence to accept challenges in honing the skills. Therefore, there is no much gap between the total no. of students and no. of students selected in placement drives. To develop the competency skills, self-interest and a roaring zeal is essential required within the students. And this zeal can be ignited among students with an excellent fluency in their interactive skill in English. This study will enhance further studies on the undergraduate engineers in Odisha and throughout India regarding the role of English faculties and technical faculties playing their respective roles in building the requisite skills within students to be a competitor of the technical age and be employed.

Entrepreneurship Skills:

Diploma Engineering course has been designed to empower the youth with employability skills. Students in this course learn the very root engineering concepts and technical skills, also a sharp practical knowledge of their branch. They can utilize the basic engineering skills for a start-up business. Here again for all kinds of document preparations, a business mindset with better leadership skills, teamwork spirit, interaction ability, negotiation skill, decision-making

and conflict management skill is highly preferred. All step-wise procedures in the making of an entrepreneur, demands high hand skills of convincing ability in each progressive step to be an entrepreneur. Both speaking and writing skills as a “must-have skill” plays a vital role in getting established as an entrepreneur. This skill builds skilled workforce which supports economic growth and advance in technology in different sectors. And a better flare in the corporate language makes the journey possible and adventurous with a confident personality. Both the technical and practical engineering skills is to be transformed with proper and appropriate guidance in required language to the technicians for successful projects works. Here negotiation, as a survival skill plays an important role. This skill with a formal discussion handles business deals successfully (S. Ammani, 2020, Page-8).

As students pursue the diploma course with limited investments for an entry into job market, it's necessary to train them rigorously on soft skills and life skills for their sustainable development. With employment and financial independence to teenagers, the economic development becomes possible which then plays a vital role for nation-building.

Engineering and Social Upliftment:

Nearly 30 to 40% of students in Diploma Engineering Course come from economically weaker class and many others whose parents with only high school education aspire a good career for their child. They avail the welfare schemes as declared by State Governments to pursue the 3 years course. These students are very much focused in better academic performance with target on campus drives. When students are well-equipped with required skills, they navigate any obstacle in their career path. Therefore, the training classes on technical skills, soft skills and life skills need to be productively implemented in the undergraduate engineers for better academic results and then 100% placements. These skills build an aspiration and confidence within students to appear both the written exams and the Personal Interviews of campus placements. Mere paper degrees are not sufficient to get an entry to industry as employers look for candidates with transferable skills to execute diversified tasks at the workplaces (M.S. Rao, 2022, Page-168).

Implementation of training classes in undergraduate engineering institutes can yield productive results providing a settled career to students with career readiness. The 21st century employability skills can encourage all diploma students to opt for placement drives and be settled with job. Employment to teenagers makes students a responsible person. Being employed these students from weak financial background shoulder financial responsibility and provide a better standard of living to parents.

Career Counselling by English faculties:

Keeping in the placement drives in mind, from beginning of 1st semester language faculties can play an important role in developing a rich thought process within the teenagers to improve in their LSRW Skills. Mainly the speaking and writing skills helps students for involvement in classroom interactions and write answers in an organized manner. A target-oriented guidance through counselling yields good results in all internal exams and also better involvement with dedication in practical classes. An enthusiastic approach by students in reading, learning and memorizing the technical concepts and fundamentals of technical skills improves their creative and analytical thinking. Apart from these, Soft Skills and People's Skills provides a richness to students in each semester like being in a preparatory ground of – “in the making of an engineer”. This inspiration will drive a passion within them to land in a job and be in the Earning Group of the society providing financial support to parents. But why

such counselling is not adopted as a target for successful result analysis in Diploma Engineering Institutions in Bhubaneswar, Odisha? The study will undoubtedly inspire impactful research works in this area. This counselling procedure will root out educated unemployment and lead the society towards an empowered self-sufficient society as youth population in India is the highest in the world.

Research Objectives:

- i) To develop the interactive skills of the students with LSRW skills to express technical ideas comfortably
- ii) To create a zeal in students for better presentation skills and online software courses
- iii) To equip students with technical skills, computer skills, interpersonal skills, and life skills for start-up business
- iv) To increase the employment % of the undergraduate engineers for socio-economic upliftment
- v) To empower the nation by supporting the youth to be financially stable from a young age to build a self-sufficient society

2. METHODOLOGY

The present research study has used the secondary data for collect of information. This study covers the geographical area of 4 no. of diploma engineering institutes at Bhubaneswar. The data has been collected by a detail discussion with the In-Charge Trainers and Placement officers of Training & Placement Cell of the respective institutions and also through a face-to-face formal meeting with HRs during the Campus drives. The past literature reviews, journals, lecture deliberations on English language skills in engineering courses from authentic internet sites has provided ample quantity of data to fulfil the objectives of the research work. In addition to this, the researcher's personal observation of case studies of successful career-goal of students from economically weaker section has also been undertaken for the study.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Renu Verma (2024) has clearly highlighted that since many decades, higher education and economic development as two sides of the same coin has brought a great appreciable development of the social status of the people. Engineering programs with its integrated practical experience through internship trainings and soft skills has contributed in the development of skilled and knowledgeable workforce. The collaboration of technical institutes and Industry has stimulated economic activities. Further with start-ups and spin-offs in technical research has led to job creation and economic diversification. Various welfare schemes of government like scholarships and grants are made accessible to underprivileged and disadvantaged groups to foster social mobility and reduce economic disparities. By expanding access to technical education, government aims at a more equitable distribution of income and wealth.

Totan Shaikh (2020) has mentioned that the establishment of technical institutions has brought a considerable development of Socio-economic conditions of India since 1944. But its growth remained slow till India became Independent. Radha Krishnan Commission, Muralidhar Commission and Kothari Commission have played a significant role in the establishment of technical education in India. After independence, the Five-Year Plans

improved the progress of technical education. Also in the early 20th century, Mr. Jamshedji Tata emphasized on the significance of scientific and technical education to fulfill the process of development of country. The independent India with its great leaders considered technical education is essential for economic development of the country which can pave a way in 'improving the quality of life of the people'.

Mr. B. Sanyasi Rao (2020) very clearly stated the inability of the technical student in communicating the technical knowledge acquired during their studentship. The gap between the industry expectations and the training provided in engineering institutions need to be taken seriously to overcome the problem of educated unemployment of engineering students.

M.S. Rao (2022) has highlighted on low employability skills of the engineering students. The main reason being the lack of communication skills. Only an effective communication skill empowers student with the decision -making skills, problem-solving skills, negotiation skills etc. Students expect to settle their career with campus placements but without soft skills, they fail to crack interviews. Industries also demand that institutions should impart employability skills to enable students eligible for job.

India Skills Report (2025) has emphasized that to create a globalized workforce, there is an urgent need to develop trained students with survival skills like -adaptability, cross-cultural competence and digital fluency along with technical skills. Skill India Digital Hub can also take initiatives to train technocrats on digital technologies to overcome the skill gaps. With rise in the employment curve the living standard of people in all communities can improve.

Preeti Dixit (2023) has mentioned the undergraduate engineering courses plays a significant role in creating jobs by equipping in-demand skills in students. These skills help engineers to work effectively and thus improves productivity in industries. Thus, the course provides stable employment and as such brings an over-all improvement in the well-being of the society. In Singapore, its world class technical institutions with high-quality trainings have skilled workforce which contributes to the over-all economic development.

Muhamad Shafaq Bin Abdul Rashid (2018) has highlighted on the acquisition of the necessary employability skills by the technocrats to be employed in the "knowledge-driven" global economy. Both critical thinking and problem-solving skills can be acquired in the best way through project-based learning and work -integrated learning with a sound interactive skill in English. Such skills generate productive workforce to meet the continual changing work place environment.

Ramanujam Meganathan (2020) has stated the uneasiness of the undergraduate engineers in acquiring communicative skills as well as proficiency in language skills to work in both academic and professional settings. There is no provision for the diploma engineering students within 18+ years of age for adequate training classes on presentation skills. Mr. R. Meganathan's research work finds a lot of lacunae in practice of English language in engineering institutes. English is an essential vehicle for expression of technical skills and also for an entry to the ever-changing workplace of 21st Century.

Mohamed Rabie (2023) has highlighted that learning the international language along with the national language is an investment in human capital. Such a broaden outlook helps to overcome the cultural barriers and wide opens door of business relationships in multiple nations with easiness and mutual understanding.

[www.quora.com\(What-is-the-importance-of-English-to-a-software-engineer\)](https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-importance-of-English-to-a-software-engineer) has highlighted on the interdependence of Software works and English Language that – all technical documentation is maintained in English Language as many teams are international. English facilitates effective communication among teams, clients and stakeholders. All collaboration tools and platforms primarily use English. Software engineers work in international level and have to meet the global market needs. Software networking, meetups, discussions, tech conference use the English language.

4. FINDINGS

Taking into consideration the training classes of the institutions, it becomes crystal clear that there is lack of importance for the training classes. Every effort is only on the syllabus completion. As such students have no idea of career goals. At best 2 to 3 classes are arranged only for the countable number of students having a demand for job immediately with completion of the course. The objective of the diploma engineering is hardly taken into consideration. The Training Placement Cell of the institution organizes campus drive. But major constraints are training on employment skills and career counselling. The resultant is only the needy students with their self- interest and zeal remain updated with self-preparation on soft skills from numerous internet sites. Major % of students display casual nature, dullness with no zeal to seat in campus drives. Fault lies in the inadequate training classes and not with students as they are in teenage group with hardly any futuristic vision and life experiences.

Above all, the study finds insufficient research works basically on the objectives of diploma engineering education. This course is a low investment professional course with the main aim to empower the students with employability skills and thus enable them to get a job. 40% of the students in diploma engineering course come from economically weaker section and therefore the diploma institutions and faculties need to act as caretakers of the students to inbuild the language skills, technical skills, computer skills along with survival skills to be an ardent participant of the community of engineers and contribute in nation-building.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The present age is the Age of Digital Technology. And English language is the only dominant international language of software development and the vehicle of expression of all the different employability skills. Among all skills, interactive skills and people's skills caters to the industry needs. Also, employers of corporate sectors prefer trained employees as they are "productive and less management." Odisha has in total more than 100 no. of diploma engineering institutes. Therefore, along with quality education, effective training classes with career counselling sessions need to be given priority to enable students to improve in academic performance to be employed with completion of the course. Life skill trainings and faculty development programmes for faculties can equip them with different activity-oriented classroom teaching methods. They need to shoulder responsibilities to their respective departments to undertaken the hardships to impart technical training and language faculties need to train students with presentation skills; also share the mock interview videos in students WhatsApp groups to overcome the non-availability of training classes on regular basis.

Moreover, the collaboration between the undergraduate engineering institutions and stakeholders can successfully fulfil the objectives of diploma engineering education in bringing a rise in socio-economic condition of the people. Further impactful research work is urgently required in this regard. In all developed nations, diploma engineering education plays a

significant role in providing employment opportunities leading to economic developments. Thus, there is a need for united effort of all stakeholders to hold the flagship to develop the survival skills and soft skills within the technocrats. With employment to the youth, all members of society and communities will have a better standard of living in a safe, secured and self-sufficient society.

References

- 1) Dr. Renu Verma (2024, Vol.-VII Issue -II, Page – 56 & 57), The Role of Higher Education in Economic Development
- 2) Totan Shaikh (2020, Page- 1 to 7), Development of Technical education in India (1945 to 1964): A Study
- 3) Mr. B. Sanyasi Rao (2020), English Language Proficiency of the Professional Students & expectations of the Engineering Industry
- 4) M.S. Rao (2022, Page- 167,168), Soft Skills Enhancing Employability, Edition- 2022
- 5) S. Ammani (Dec.2020, Chap.- 1Page-8), The IUP Journal of Soft Skills, Chapter- 1 – Blended Learning of Soft Skills Through Life Skills in an Organisation
- 6) India Skills Report (2025)
- 7) Engr. Mrs. Funmi Akingbagbohun (2018), Lecture delivered on Role of Engineers in National Economy Development (2018)
- 8) Preeti Dixit (Sep.2023, Page- 61,62), The impact of vocational education on economic growth and development across the G20 countries
- 9) Muhamad Shafaq Bin Abdul Rashid (2018), Teaching Methods That Enhance the Development of Technical and Vocational Students Employability
- 10) Ramanujam Meganathan (2020, Page-26,27), Research in English Language Education in India
- 11) Mohamed Rabie (2023, Page -1,3), Language and Life Berlina A. Lopes (2021), English in India today: A Journey from Foreign to Native
- 12) Lakshminarayan Samavedham (2008), Facilitating 21st Century Skills in Engineering Students
- 13) Ht Van Der Molen (2007), Personality Characteristic of Engineers Clara Viegas (2021, Page- 1 & 2), Engineering Education: New Challenges, New Approaches

Online Materials:

- 1) <https://www.esilv.fr/en/why-engineers-make-great-entrepreneurs/#>
- 2) <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/economics/09/education-training->
- 3) <https://ghrcemn.raisoni.net/why-pursuing-a-diploma-in-engineering>
- 4) <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-importance-of-English-to-a-software-engineer>